

THE MAPLE LEAF BUILDING CASE

Project background:

The Maple Leaf building was a medium-sized commercial refurbishment project located on Penn Street, a busy commercial area in Peterborough. Specifically, an architectural project aimed at fitting out an office building. The project was carried out at the cost of £15million. The scope of works, initially, included:

- Removal of existing windows and replacement with new ones
- New stone reveals to front window openings. This requirement was later dropped by the Client on cost grounds
- Modification to staircase core and water closets (WCs)
- Improved reception area and new external entrance canopy
- Revised roof plant room strategy, access and plant enclosure extension
- Modification to rear parking areas with new electrical substation
- Internal office fit-out to category A, including chilled beams, ceiling and raised floors (Essentially, a provision of a basic shell for tenants to provide their own final fit-outs)
- Complete new air conditioning , mechanical & electrical services
- Removal of screed to existing office floors to maximise headroom (with the exception of ground floor offices). The new mechanical installations required to be accommodated in the ceiling necessitated a deeper ceiling than the existing one. This meant a reduced room height which was going to undermine the Client's letting price and project profitability. Hence, the existing 75mm screed was to be removed on all five floors and a new floor finish applied to increase the room height. This intervention was to contribute, at least, an additional 50mm to the overall room height.

Exhibit 1 indicates the front elevation of the Maple Leaf Building.

Exhibit 1: Front elevation of the Maple Leaf building

The project procurement strategy was officially design and build (D&B). However, the Client who was a matured commercial developer and was well aware of the pros and cons of D&B, decided to engage a design firm to handle some of the designs upfront. On the other hand, the Client wanted Contractors' specialist inputs in the project development and hence settled for a D&B. The Lead Designers (i.e. Architects) were appointed Principal Designers (PDs) of the project and kept throughout. Although the project was officially conceived as a D&B, it was implemented as a traditional contract. The D&B aspect of the project was with payments. The Client paid the D&B contractor who subsequently paid the sub-contractors.

Client's General Health and Safety (H&S) Arrangements

The Client was not very knowledgeable regarding Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 (CDM 2015) issues and thus engaged the services of a Project Manager who had knowledge of such issues to provide support in that respect at the outset of the project. This practice highlights an arrangement in the industry where some project Clients when faced with the challenge of complying with the Regulations (i.e. CDM 2015) regarding H&S arrangements fall on project managers. This phenomenon manifests in two forms as: Clients relying on project managers to convene and coordinate design review meetings; as well as Clients listing project managers as CDM Clients and letting them assume Clients H&S duties on projects. Further, the appointment of the PD sequel to the Project Manager in respect of H&S risk management on the project brings to the fore Clients and their appointees' recognition of the formal arrangements expected on projects, at least from a regulatory perspective. Additionally, this arrangement underlines another practice in the industry where Clients depend on third party entities like PDs, CDM advisors and H&S consultants to support their H&S arrangements. What also becomes clear here is that, in practice, Clients can employ a mix of approaches as far as their suitable arrangements for H&S is concerned. Perhaps, what is not clear and may require further investigation is how well these mixed approaches work in reality.

The project team consisted the Architects, Structural Engineers, Services Engineers, Cost Consultants, an Approved Inspector, a PD and Principal Contractor (PC). The Architects, who were the first to be appointed among the Designers, had done previous schemes for the Client. The satisfactory outcomes of the previous schemes made a case for their appointment as PDs on the current project. The Client representatives (i.e. the Project Manager and Cost Consultants) organised the tendering process with partially-developed drawings and other pre-construction information generated by the project Architects and PD. The PD was not involved in the tendering process as the Client deemed the process to be commercially sensitive. In all, there were five tenderers who tendered for the project. The lowest evaluated tenderer was selected for the project subsequently. The Client appointed the Main Contractor as the Principal Contractor for the project.

The entire team, with the exception of the Main Contractor (i.e. PC), was put together by the Client's Project Manager with the assistance of the PD. In the assessment process, considerations were made to membership of professional bodies such as Association for Project Safety (APS), Institution of Structural Engineers (IStructE), Chartered Institution of Building

Services Engineers (CIBSE), and Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS) for the relevant design disciplines. The National Examination Board in Occupational Safety and Health (NEBOSH) certification was required for the Main Contractor. Besides, relevant and specific experiences of individual project team members, with focus on H&S, were emphasised as part of the competence assessment. This was done through the review of CVs by the PD. Additionally, a standard questionnaire was sent to all prospective appointees for their completion and return. Following the return of the completed questionnaires, an interview session (coordinated by the PD) was organised to aid the competence-appraisal process of the appointees. Exhibits 2 and 3 indicate the standard questionnaires for the Designers and the PC, respectively.

The assistance offered by the PD to the Client in respect of getting the right people to the project highlights a pervasive practice in the industry (i.e. bespoke use of repeat appointment of dutyholders already assessed for skills, knowledge, experience [SKE]) regarding assembling the project supply chain with focus on H&S. Additionally, the PD's role in ensuring that other project participants are competent, particularly from a H&S perspective, is not a duty of the PD but often carried out as Client expectation. This unearths an extra vital but non-regulatory PD function in the industry.

The scope of what the PD was supposed to do, specifically, on the project regarding H&S risk management was based on the Association for Project Safety (APS) PD agreement and was not to go beyond that. Further, the contract of engagement as Designers (i.e. Architects) was separate from that of appointment as a PD. The PD was engaged throughout the project, right from pre-planning stage (where negotiations with local planning authorities on the façade and canopy extension to the building due to proximity to a busy street were done) to handover. In terms of actual PD work on the project, about half a day per week was committed.

The readily available spaces in the existing building offered an advantage for some of the floors to be used as site offices and welfare areas, albeit with the inconvenience of regular relocations as the work progressed. Further, existing stair cases were used for access as well as lift for the movement of materials and workmen. See Exhibit 4 for such utilisation of spaces.

Budget for the PD services was generally based on a percentage of the contract sum. The percentage allowed was relatively higher than a new build due to the peculiar nature of refurbishment works. In establishing the percentage value, considerations were made to the site investigation efforts; work opening ups; iterative designing efforts due to the emergence of new issues and risks as the work progressed, particularly with refurbishment works. Specifically, on this project, there was the need for recoring which required the introduction of a new void, steel beams as well as risers. This presented some degree of complexity. Even though the PD services fee was integrated with the general design fee which overall was four percent (4%) of the contract sum, the precise percentage of the total was about 0.5 percent (0.5%). Similarly, the other Designers also built their duties under the CDM Regulations 2015 into their professional fees.

Generally, the H&S arrangements for the project was considered proportionate and worked well.

Organisation:

There was no specific organogram for the way H&S safety was managed on the project. Instead, a simple responsibility matrix indicating the major professional services, their roles, and the entities involved was used. This matrix was also indicated on the CDM strategy brief to provide, at a glance, useful information among project team members. This information related to entities who are responsible, accountable, may be consulted, and informed regarding certain aspects and risks related to the project. Exhibit 5 indicates the simple responsibility matrix for the project.

Regarding how the Architects (who doubled as the PDs on the project) were organised to deliver H&S services effectively on the project, the design firm had a technical team made of Architects with different specialisations such as: fire, accessibility and inclusive design, H&S, among others. These specialists were often not involved in day-to-day management of specific projects but offered specialist supports to several projects being handled by their design firm at any point in time. Project Architects were required to handle day-to-day H&S issues on the project and escalate difficult and challenging ones to the specialist(s) in the technical team for redress. However, during recessions or periods of lower number of projects, they are allocated to specific projects for day-to-day administration.

Principal CDM Documents Preparation:

The preparation of the pre-construction information (PCI) started at the pre-planning stage when the Architects (i.e. PDs) were appointed. This included the compilation of:

- photographs of existing entrance and proposed modifications,
- site plan/access,
- proposed site establishment layout,
- proposed plans,
- demolition drawings,
- Information on H&S analysis of building features such as plant location and access. For instance, as indicated in Exhibit 6, two options (i.e. a broad staircase and a companionway ladder) for a safe access to roof top plants were presented for choice by the Client. The Client eventually chose the companionway ladder option on the basis of cost.

The CDM strategy brief was the main tool for the assembly and dissemination of PCI among project parties. This tool adopted an approach which aimed at visualising PCI information for ease of interpretation, assimilation and exploitation among relevant project parties – a practice which is still at an embryonic stage in the industry.

Exhibits 7a – 7f indicate excerpts of PCI as captured in the project's CDM strategy brief.

The preparation of the Construction Phase Plan (CPP) was started immediately the Main Contractor was selected. A phenomenon which confirms an approach in the industry where there is an early preparation of the CPP by the Principal Contractor in tandem with the design process. This arrangement often happens on D&B projects and in some cases even on traditional design-bid-build projects where there are arrangements for early contractor involvement. The advantage with this approach is that it gives considerable amount of time to the other pre-construction dutyholders to provide meaningful reviews and inputs to the CPP

before commencement of project on site. Information for the preparation of the CPP mainly came from the CDM strategy brief. Its adequacy was checked by the PD.

The Health and Safety File (HSF) preparation commenced with the compilation of the CDM strategy brief. This document evolved with the project development process and eventually added to the HSF. Additionally, the PD supplied a template of information requirements regarding the HSF to all relevant project parties upon their appointments by the Client. The template was to serve as a guide in respect of what specific information and the form in which it would be required for the purpose of the HSF. Information placed in the HSF included: as-built drawings, operation and maintenance (O&M) manuals, among others. A sample of the template is indicated in Exhibit 8.

Information in the CDM strategy brief were contributed by the PD, Architects, Structural Engineer, Services Engineers, and Contractors. There were no serious challenges in the compilation of the principal CDM documents, largely due to the effectiveness of the CDM strategy brief tool.

Coordination:

Coordination of the inputs of the different dutyholders was handled via meetings and e-mails. There was no deployment of a common data environment platform for coordination purposes. Design team meetings were held every two weeks among the design team members during the pre-construction stage to address design-related challenges including H&S safety. An excerpt of a typical meeting agenda is indicated in Exhibit 9. Such meetings included the Project Architects (PD), Structural Engineers, Cost Consultants, Services Engineers, Project Manager and the PC (after its appointment). Discipline Designers presented their drawings at meetings with comments and proposals proffered by other team members. Commonly agreed proposals and decisions were recorded by the PD in minutes which served as source or input documents for revising the CDM strategy brief document as the design progressed. The updated CDM strategy brief was subsequently shared with all project team members to keep every team member at the same level of knowledge regarding project H&S risks and management. Additionally, at the pre-construction stage, Client progress meetings were held to inform the Client of developments on the project. This often took place immediately after design team meetings with the Client in attendance. **Both** meetings were often convened and coordinated by the PD.

There was low level temporary works involved in the project except for the new core that needed to be created in existing slabs to provide access to an air duct running from the roof top to the ground floor. The slabs required propping during the cutting process with new steel beams introduced to provide support in its operation. There was, therefore, a close engagement between the Structural Engineer and the PC regarding that work. Precisely, the Structural Engineer proposed the construction methodology for handling that aspect of work with a general oversight by the PD. Exhibits 10 and 11 indicate the revised core design and the arrangement of the new steel beam support to the slabs proposed by the Structural Engineer, respectively.

Generally, efforts on design H&S risk management were not isolated on the project. They were deeply integrated with every aspect and process in the project development, particularly at

discussions during design and Client progress meetings. Specific H&S risk issues were highlighted by the PD to the PC, at design team meetings, for particular attention and management. This included:

- Minimisation of manual handling of materials and work processes. For instance, due to the large area required for screed removal, the PD recommended maximisation of mechanised approaches to alleviate the health impact of that operation to workmen.
- Strict adherence to usage of safety equipment by every person on site including Client agents who would occasionally visit the site.
- The use of vacuum extraction instead of water suppressant as a water suppressant approach was not appropriate for an existing building. Again, a vacuum extraction of dust was recommended due to the indoor nature of most of the project activities.

All of these identified significant risks were captured by the CDM strategy brief document. An Excerpt of these in the CDM strategy brief are indicated in Exhibit 12.

The existing building had a poor **access** protection system at the roof top. Precisely, there were only poles with ropes to prevent persons needed to use that space from falling off. The PD was particularly concerned about this situation and pointed it out at design team meetings. The proposed scheme, thus, provided a proper man-safety system to address this safety risk. See Exhibit 13a - 13b for arrangements of existing and proposed safety systems at the roof top.

At design team meetings, the PD encouraged good practice by highlighting H&S risks associated with the project, suggested and invited ideas on remedial measures from other project team members. The identified significant risks and their remedial measures were captured in the CDM strategy brief. Further, significant H&S risks were recommended by the PD, in addition to the CDM strategy brief, to be notified on drawings for the attention of all relevant project parties. These approaches (i.e. use of CDM strategy brief with attendant photos of risks, and annotated drawings) employed a visualisation technique to highlight and manage H&S risks on projects. For instance, the proposed scheme required bigger and heavy mechanical plants to be installed at the roof top. The existing access to the roof top, which was a pull-down ladder, was deemed unacceptable, risky and needed to be replaced with a wider and more stable access via the staircase area. In addition, mechanical plants located very close to the edge of the roof were to be provided with acoustic roof plant enclosures to prevent persons falling off the roof as well as to minimise noise pollution by the plants. The entire roof perimeter, and a narrow point in the roof access, was highlighted to be protected throughout construction and replaced with a man-safety system upon practical completion. Exhibits 14a and 14b indicate the visualisation technique for managing H&S risks and the proposed roof access, respectively. The project was considered relatively challenge-free regarding design H&S risk management.

Conclusions and lessons:

With the stock of buildings (particularly commercial ones) at the urban cores aging, coupled with increasing modernisation, refurbishment works have become inevitable and are increasing in volume. This phenomenon presents a challenge to the construction industry, mainly from a H&S perspective. As observed in this Maple Leaf building project, refurbishment projects pose more health risk challenges compared to new builds. This is because of the potentially

significant cuttings, hackings, drillings, and opening ups associated with refurbishment projects. These activities generate considerable amount of dust. Further, as the knowledge of prevention through design (i.e. pursuit of designs that are inherently safe) emerged about three decades ago, most likely, old buildings may not possess the attributes of inherent safety. Hence, refurbishment works which may also aim at enhancing the safety attributes of such buildings could pose safety risks to the workmen during the construction stage. Hence, Designer awareness in relation to this risk must be enhanced in the industry. This case presents a number of useful lessons that may benefit future projects regarding H&S risks management and these include the following:

- The use of the CDM strategy brief toolkit – which pooled together all significant H&S risks as well as proposed measures to address them in a single document – focused and kept all project team participants’ eyes on the ball in respect of H&S risks management.
- The CDM analysis of relevant features of the building with solution options to identified H&S risks, as contained in the CDM strategy brief toolkit, provided opportunity for the project Client to meaningfully contribute to H&S risk management on the project. This encouraged the Client support for H&S risk management on the project as the fear of increased project cost due to H&S design considerations was assuaged.
- Clients’ commercial interests can have H&S implications for projects. Such interests may require modifications to project features, particularly refurbishment projects, which would have significant H&S consequences. Compared to new builds, refurbishment projects by nature offer limitations to design options when viewed from Clients’ objectives for construction products. It is at the confluence of these inherent limitations and Client objectives that significant H&S risks emanate on refurbishment projects. Hence, project parties must be extra-conscious of H&S risks when dealing with refurbishment projects. Further, the expectations of Clients for refurbishment projects should be moderated, where necessary, to ensure optimal H&S performance on such projects.

EXHIBITS

Exhibit 2: A sample of standard questionnaire for Designers' organisational capability assessment

1 Company Details	Response/Comment
1.1 Company Name:	
1.2 Head Office (Registered Office):	
1.3 Correspondence address (if different to above):	
1.4 Date trading commenced:	
1.5 Type of Company (Limited, partnership sole trader, etc.):	
1.6 Contact Details:	
2 Types of Service(s) Provided	
2.1 Services Provided:	
2.2 Please provide details of similar projects undertaken by yourselves:	
3 Health & Safety (H&S) Policy	
3.1 Please provide a copy of your current general H&S policy statement:	
3.2 Please provide a copy of your management organisation chart highlighting those with H&S responsibilities:	
3.3 Please provide details of your company management system, in particular your H&S management system and other arrangements for putting the H&S policy into effect:	
4 Insurance	
4.1 Please provide a copy of your insurance certificate that applies to the work you perform or intend to perform for..... (e.g. Employers Liability, Public Liability, Contractors All Risks, Construction Plant and Professional Indemnity):	
4.2 Has your Insurer made any conditions on your policy within the last 3 years? (If so, please provide details):	
Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 (CDM 2015)	
5.1 Please confirm you understand the requirements of Regulation 8, General duties of	

the CDM 2015, and explain how your organisation meets them.	
5.2 Please confirm you understand the requirements of Regulations 9 and 10, Designer duties of the CDM 2015, and explain how your organisation meets them.	
5.3 Please confirm you understand the general principles of prevention. Please give examples of how you achieve these during your works.	
5.4 Please provide details on how your organisation deals with foreseeable and significant risks to the health or safety of any persons – (a) Carrying out or liable to be affected by construction work (b) Maintaining or cleaning a structure (c) Using a structure as a workplace	
5.5 Please provide details on how you communicate to other parties such as the Client, Principal Designer, Principal Contractor and other Designers to provide them with information about the design, construction or maintenance of structures.	
6 Health and Safety Resources	
6.1 Please provide relevant H&S certification for the members of staff involved in these types of project:	
6.2 Please provide the names and qualifications of internal H&S advisors and/external H&S consultants used by your organisation:	
6.3 Please outline any specialist resources which are utilised by your organisation in an advisory capacity in H&S:	
6.4 Please describe how each member of the team is communicated with, so that they are aware of his/her responsibilities under the CDM 2015.	
7 Training and Information	
7.1 Please provide details of Designers H&S training, in particular training focusing on health and safety in design.	
7.2 Please provide details of your CPD programme.	
7.3 Please provide details of key project personnel [Names, CV's, qualifications, memberships etc]	
7.4 Please provide evidence of the Designers experience with similar projects.	

7.5 Provide brief details of similar design projects undertaken [locations, description, dates, size and cost]	
7.6 Provide references from those who have engaged the Designers on similar projects	
8 Resources and Workforce Involvement	
8.1 Please outline how you allocate sufficient time and resources when planning and delivering projects you are engaged in	
8.2 Please provide details of the number of competent personnel available to work on the projects	
8.3 Please provide details of design and technical support facilities [e.g. computing, health and safety guidance, specialist technical links with external experts etc]	
8.4 Please provide evidence of health and safety consultation with the workforce [names of safety representatives, records of health and safety meetings/committees etc]	
9 Monitoring, Audit and Review	
9.1 Please provide details of the monitoring, audit and review procedures for your H&S systems. Including evidence of any audits that the management responded to.	
10 Hazard Elimination and Risk Control	
10.1 Please Provide details on how you ensure co-operation with the design team, other designers, contractors and the Principal Designer.	
10.2 Please provide details on how hazards are eliminated and any remaining risks are controlled including examples of your design risk assessment system.	
10.3 Please provide examples of how risks have been reduced by your designs.	
10.4 Please provide confirmation that any structure used as a workplace will meet the requirements of the Workplace [Health Safety and Welfare] Regulations 1992. Please provide examples on how this has been achieved on projects you have carried out.	
10.5 Please provide details on how you will provide adequate information with your designs	

and information needed for the health and safety file.	
11 Sub-Contracting/Consulting Procedures	
11.1 Please provide evidence showing how you ensure sub-contractors/consultants have sufficient skills, knowledge and experience to undertake their works for yourselves	
11.2 Will you be engaging or commissioning other persons to carry out designs on your behalf for this project [If so, please provide details of them and how you monitor their activities]:	
12 Accident Reporting, Enforcement and Investigation	
12.1 Please provide details on how you record and investigate accidents.	
12.2 Please provide details of any intervention or enforcement action taken over the last 5 years and actions taken to prevent recurrence.	
Further information	
Please provide any further information which you think will assist in assessing your skills, knowledge, experience and organisational capability.	

We undertake to provide the designated designer adequate time and technical support facilities to fulfil the requirements under Regulations 8, 9 and 10 of the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015.

Signed:

On behalf of (Company Name):

Date:

Signed:
.....

Date:
.....

Director/Partner Responsible for Health & Safety

Exhibit 3: A sample of standard questionnaire for Principal Contractor’s organisational capability assessment

Questionnaire Checklist	Response/Comment
1 Health and Safety Policy	
1.1 Provide a copy of your Health and Safety Policy Statement.	
1.2 Provide a copy of your management organisation chart, complete with details of the health and safety team.	
2 Arrangements	
2.1 Provide details of your company Management System, in particular your Health and Safety Management System and any other arrangements for putting the Health and Safety Policy into effect.	
3 Competent Advice	
3.1 Please provide the name and competency details of your source of health and safety advice.	
4 Training and Information	
4.1 Provide details of a Health and Safety training culture to include records, certificates and adequate H&S induction training for site based personnel.	
4.2 Provide details of an active CPD programme.	
5 Individual Qualifications and Experience	
5.1 Provide details (names and CV’s) of key project personnel identifying their skills, knowledge, experience and training to carry out and manage the works.	
5.2 Provide evidence of experience with similar projects for project personnel.	
5.3 Give brief details of similar projects undertaken (locations, description, dates,	

size and cost) by the company. Include a reference contact for previous Clients.	
6 Monitoring, audit and review	
6.1 Provide details of the monitoring, audit and review procedures for your health and safety systems. Include evidence of any audits and the management responses.	
7 Resources and workforce involvement	
7.1 Give details on the number of competent personnel available to work on the project.	
7.2 Provide details of the technical resources available to assist project personnel in the implementation of the project. (e.g. computing, health and safety guidance, specialist technical links with external experts etc.)	
7.3 Provide evidence of health and safety consultation with workforce (names of safety representatives, records of health and safety meetings/committees etc).	
8 Accident reporting, enforcement & investigation	
8.1 Give details on the way in which you record and investigate accidents and incidents, giving details of the last 2 accidents and actions taken to prevent recurrence.	
8.2 Provide details of any enforcement action taken over the last 5 years and actions taken to put matters right.	
8.3 Provide details of your accident statistics for the last 3 years and their basis.	
9 Sub-contracting, consulting procedures	
9.1 Provide evidence showing how you ensure sub-contractors/consultants are competent.	
9.2 Give details showing how you monitor the performance of subcontractors.	
10 Risk assessment	
10.1 Provide evidence showing how the	

company will identify significant H&S risks and how they will be controlled.	
10.2 Provide samples of risk assessments/safe systems of work/method statements.	
11 Co-operation and co-ordination	
11.1 Provide evidence of how the company co-ordinates its work with others.	
12 Further information	
12.1 Provide any further information which you think will help assess your competence and resources	

Exhibit 4: Utilisation of existing spaces for welfare, offices and materials conveyance

CDM Strategy brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :- 4	Revision & Date:	2nd Revision	20 th May 2019			
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
2.4 EXISTING GROUND FLOOR PLAN WITH INDICATED WELFARE FACILITIES AND SERVICE LIFT FOR MATERIALS HOISTING	<p>The diagram is a ground floor plan of the Maple Leaf Building. Key features include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Client Conference Room: Located at the top left. Hoist: A vertical structure in the center. WELFARE AREA: A red-outlined area to the right of the hoist. WC: A red-outlined area below the welfare area. BWF Site Offices: A red-outlined area at the bottom center. West Stairs: Located on the right side, with a callout stating 'West Stairs 1. Ground to 3rd upto 18th April, then upto 2nd only'. East Stairs: Located on the left side, with a callout stating 'East Stairs to L. Ground and 3rd Floors'. Lifts: A callout at the bottom right states 'Lifts usable for hoisting and waste upto 3rd until April 18th'. Alexandra Road: Labeled at the bottom of the plan. Scale: 1:100. </p>						<p>GROUND FLOOR PLAN</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Welfare facilities are provided at ground floor level by retaining WC's offices and rest, locker areas until area needs refurbishment. OR Temporary welfare facilities can be provided in serviceyard below building in latter stages of project Lift usable until 18th April after which Hoist location suggested for materials distribution and waste removal. Windows removed for access at every level Scaffolding to elevations to be agreed on the basis of need for external access to replace windows and stone reveals. 			
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 5: Simple responsibility matrix for the project

Project participant	Organisation	Role
Client	Parker Realty	Project funding
Project Manager	Bay Ltd	Project administration and management
Project Architect	Spaysis	Architectural designs services
Principal Designer	Spaysis	Design H&S risk management
Structural Engineer	BM Consult	Structural design services
Services Engineer	Solar Engineering	Building services design
Cost Consultant	PA Consult	Project cost management
Approved Inspector	Jay Wood	Building regulation and approval services
Principal Contractor	Limex	Construction H&S risk management
Main Contractor	Limex	Construction services

Exhibit 6: CDM analysis options for a broad staircase and a companionway ladder

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management						ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS																			
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019																	
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References																		
3.7- REVISED ROOF ACCESS ALTERNATIVES: BROAD STAIRCASE VS. COMPANIONWAY LADDER							<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preferred roof access option is companionway ladder with lifting beam above for heavy items of plant. 2. Structural alterations to staircase and plantroom roof slab 3. Access door at base of companionway ladder to open outwards onto landing 4. Client to ensure a permit to work system for roof access due to low parapets . 5. Work at height training required for all operatives unless a perimeter handrail is provided during construction <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px; text-align: center;">Crash Deck required from March 3rd</div>																		
	<p>Team Sign -off status</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Client</td> <td>Parker Realty</td> <td>Architect</td> <td>Spaysis</td> <td>Struct. Eng</td> <td>BM Consult</td> <td>Services Eng</td> <td>Solar Eng.</td> <td>P. Contractor</td> <td>Limex</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Others</td> <td>PM</td> <td>Bay Ltd</td> <td>PD</td> <td>Spaysis</td> <td>Landscapes</td> <td>Cost Consultant</td> <td>PA Consult</td> <td>App. Insp.</td> <td>Jay Wood</td> </tr> </table>			Client	Parker Realty	Architect				Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex	Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscapes	Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.
Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex																
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscapes	Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood																

Exhibit 7a: An excerpt of PCI in CDM strategy site plan/access

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn	24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019			
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
2.2 SITE PLAN/ ACCESS						<p>Layout Sign Off</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Date: _____</p> <p>APPLICATION SITE BOUNDARY</p> <p>LAND OWNED BY AFFILIATE</p>		<p>!</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> VEHICULAR ACCESS OFF THE MAIN ROAD TO BE LEFT TURN ONLY NARROW REAR SERVICE YARD MAY RESTRICT LARGE VEHICULAR TURNING UNLESS CAN UNDERSAIL THE BUILDING 		
Team Sign -off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 7b: An excerpt of PCI in CDM strategy brief indicating photographs of existing entrance and proposed modifications

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :- 4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019			
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
2.6 - PLANNING CONDITION CONSTRUCTION TIMES	Construction Times TO BE CONFIRMED ONCE PLANNING APPROVAL OBTAINED									
3.0 PROJECT DESIGN ASPIRATIONS										
3.1 EXISTING Entrance modifications	 GLAZED ENTRANCE CANOPY <ol style="list-style-type: none"> To be built behind hoardings on pavement Future cleaning via long pole from a scaffold tower or suitable A-frame ladder 									
Secure hoardings to protect public										
3.2 PROPOSED Canopy removal and replacement with new	 <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforced concrete canopy to be removed by safe procedures . Allowances to be made for replacement canopy. Salvaged bricks to be reused to make good opening 									
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 7c: An excerpt of PCI in CDM strategy brief indicating site and service areas

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 15%; background-color: #e0ffe0; padding: 5px;"> <p>3.3 THE SITE & SERVICE AREAS VEHICULAR ACCESS , PARKED CARS, STORAGE OF MATERIALS, SITE WELFARE FACILITIES</p> <p>Vehicle Manoeuvring Area</p> <p>Car Park Area</p> <p>Main Entrance Gates & Barrier</p> </div> <div style="width: 80%; text-align: center;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access roads and vehicle circulation to be considered in relation to local road layout, building use, etc by design team 2. Project Team to discuss implications of site set-up on design , cost or safety. 3. Carrying of demolition materials into skip in car park to be considered 4. Loading of full skips and removal lorries to be considered with tight turning circles. 5. Storage containers to be provided by contractor to contain materials, tools, equipment and operatives possessions <p>Ramp wall to be demolished and bricks salvaged for entrance canopy repairs</p> </div> </div>										
Team Sign -off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 7d: An excerpt of PCI in CDM strategy brief indicating proposed site establishment layout

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
2.3 - SITE ESTABLISHMENT LOWER GROUND FLOOR PLAN & REAR SERVICE YARD	<p style="text-align: center;">Lower Ground & Site Plan</p> <p>Legend: → Pedestrian Access & Fire Escape → Vehicular access - - - 1.8m Heras Fencing</p> <p>Labels on plan: Ramp, Service Yard, Storage or parking, Main Site Entrance, Operative Main Entrance, GRINWOOD LANE, ALEXANDRA ROAD.</p> <p>Scale: 1:100</p>						<p style="text-align: center;"></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Locations of vehicle deliveries, off loading, waste collection, waste removal, materials storage, welfare facilities. Some contractor expertise may be required pre tender. Coordinated drawing required. Width of road and turning circle for large vehicles and crane to ascertain viability Client and Design Team agreed Site Set-Up Plan for the layout of site establishment. 2 Access doors and stairs to all levels. Hoarding lines and alternative personnel access points agreed 			
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 7e: An excerpt of PCI in CDM strategy brief indicating a proposed floor plan

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
2.5 PROPOSED FIRST FLOOR PLAN							<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. REVISED CORE PLAN Duct holes to be protected 2. SCREED REMOVAL all areas 3. WINDOWS REPLACED removal and replacement methods to be considered with respect to access externally, internally or both. 4. NEW CAT A FIT OUT 			
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	CDM-C	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 7f: An excerpt of PCI in CDM strategy brief indicating a demolition plan

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS E.g. References			
3.4 DEMOLITION PLANS (ALL LEVELS)						<p>1. Demolition, and strip out strategy , with waste skips locations and chute or hoisting locations to be proposed by contractor in Construction Phase Plan</p>				
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty Bay Ltd	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM		PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 8: A sample of H&S file compilation template

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Architect /Principal Designer/ Principal Contractor</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Architect, Principal Designer or the Principal Contractor, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to specify processes, which will not release the potential for harm held in the building fabric. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	General Materials and finishes. Including any deviations from the generality and their locations.			
	Paints / Adhesives: General type, location and COSHH data sheets where relevant for future maintenance / removal.			
	Roof Assemblies: Materials and where applicable non-fragile life.			
	Glazing: Type, weight (and location where unusual).			
	Provisions for future maintenance, e.g. cleaning of glass, gutters, external painting, include assumptions about how it could be carried out. i.e. cherry picker or long pole.			
	Provisions for future dismantling. Including any deviations from the generality and their locations.			
	"Final Construction" "As built" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Civil / Structural Designer</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Civil / Structural Engineer, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to specify processes, which will not release the potential for harm held in the existing structure. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	The basic structural form, e.g. a pin-jointed steel frame with bracing.			
	The methods of structural analysis, including the names of any computer programmes used.			
	How the characteristic loads (occupancy and environmental, e.g. wind) were derived. List the British or European standards used.			
	The wind loads: basic wind speed used and a brief résumé of how the building was defined for calculating wind coefficients.			
	How the structural elements in the structure were designed. List all standards (with their date) that were used.			
	Any deviations from the requirements in the listed standards.			
	Critical components and how they work, e.g. fixing of pre-cast walling.			
	Requirements for and provisions for future maintenance, e.g. repainting steel, resurfacing roads, etc.			
	How the calculations may be obtained, e.g. file reference numbers, location.			
	How the building could be demolished or dismantled.			
"Final Construction"" As Built" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format				

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Mechanical and/or Refrigeration Designer / Engineer</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Building Services Designer(s) for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to minimise the risks associated with the work required to maintain / supplement existing services. This should include, as a minimum, information about the following:</p>	Design assumptions and parameters e.g. temperature, heat loss / gains, etc.			
	A schedule of significant Plant weights and / or sizes, their locations and special lifting requirements. e.g. lifts, cranes, hoists, etc.			
	Significant hazards associated with pieces of equipment, e.g. high pressures, high temperatures, and their locations, etc.			
	Schedule of the plant and equipment installed. (Note: Do not include manufacturers catalogues or irrelevant information) Details to be included in the O&M Manual.			
	Provision for future inspections and maintenance and assumptions about how they would be carried out, e.g. from a 'cherry picker'.			
	How the services could be dismantled at end of service life.			
	Plan showing locations of incoming service isolation points.			
	"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Electrical Designer / Engineer Information to be provided by the Building Services Designer(s) for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to minimise the risks associated with the work required to maintain / supplement existing services. This should include, as a minimum, information about the following:	Design assumptions and parameters e.g. Illumination levels, etc.			
	A schedule of significant Plant weights and / or sizes, their locations and special lifting requirements.			
	Significant hazards associated with pieces of equipment, e.g. high voltages, high temperatures, and their locations, etc.			
	Schedule of the plant and equipment installed. (Note: Do not include manufacturers' catalogues or irrelevant information). Details to be included in the O&M Manual.			
	Provision for future inspections and maintenance and assumptions about how they would be carried out, e.g. from a 'cherry picker'.			
	How the services could be dismantled at end of service life.			
	Plan showing locations of incoming service isolation points.			
	"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Landscape Architect / External Services Designer(s)</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Designer(s) of the External Services, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to help designers to minimise the risks associated with working on, or close to, existing services. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	The general form of the ground that the services were installed in, including any areas of significant hazard, e.g. made ground.			
	The location of services referenced from a fixed point on the building.			
	The location of isolation points within the building.			
	The depth of the services and utilities.			
	<p>For drainage runs, the following additional information would be useful;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The falls of the drains; • The length, size and unit weight of the pipes; • The location of any drains, which carry highly hazardous waste from, e.g. pathology laboratories, petrol interceptors, etc; 			
	A manhole schedule giving diameters, depths and form of access arrangements, e.g. mild steel ladders.			
	Provisions for future maintenance, e.g. Load bearing of hardstandings, lamp replacement to road lighting, etc.			
"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format				

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Principal Contractor Information to be provided by the Principal Contractor for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to help minimise the risks associated with working on, or close to, existing services. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:	List of Subcontractors			
	List of Main Suppliers			
	O & M Manuals for Electrical, Mechanical, Refrigeration, Sprinklers, Lifts, etc. (Note: O&M Manuals to be kept as a separate document and cross referenced)			
	Product information from Nominated and Domestic Subcontractors / Suppliers relating to cleaning and maintenance of the structure, inc. COSHH data sheets where applicable.			
	Strategy for access, maintenance, cleaning, removal, renewal, de-commissioning, de-construction, demolition, etc.			
	Test Certificates / Guarantees and Warranties			
	Waste transfer documents / Air Clearance - Re-occupation Certification.			

Exhibit 9: An excerpt of design team meeting agenda

Design Team Protocol and Meeting Agenda (CDM specific items):-

1. CDM issues to be taken with all report/agenda items e.g. Client, architect, structures, services, landscape, fire, etc. Not as a stand-alone subject.
2. All CDM Significant issues (risks and benefits) to be identified and captured in Schedule and CDM analysis report & drawings, with lead action owner and priority (RAG) indicated.
3. CDM Analysis Report items to form focus for meeting discussions
4. All CDM Significant issues to be prioritised and discussed by whole team in visual project context and resolution/mitigation/future action agreed and recorded.
5. Pre-Construction Information/ CDM Design Analysis report to be updated and issued, as project issues dictate, throughout the project, and at end of Work Stages.
6. Health and Safety File format and progress to be agreed from the start of the project.

Note: - All routine/normal/generic Contractor design & construction risks to be dealt with at Contractor Progress meetings.

Exhibit 10: Revised core design

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management				ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS						
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HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >	INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References				
3.13 NEW CORE PLAN GROUND	</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Fully accessible ceiling to be provided in WC allowing access to ceiling services. Accessible rear access panels to WC plumbing for ease of maintenance. 									
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	CDM-C	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 11: New steel beam support to revised core slab

General arrangement of new steel beam support to cored slabs

Exhibit 12: Excerpts of CDM strategy brief indicating advice against musculoskeletal injuries, manual handling of work processes, and uncontrolled dust i.e. Health risk issues requiring contractor feedback in Construction Phase Plan

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management						ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS				
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5.8 LARGE, LONG AND HEAVY STEEL STRUCTURAL BEAMS	Avoidance of musculoskeletal injuries to operatives									
5.9- EXISTING SCREED REMOVAL	<p>This proposed process is highly dust , noise and hand arm vibration producing and needs considerable cost to reduce these hazardous effects</p>									
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 13a: Arrangements of existing safety system at roof top

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management							ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS						
Project & No:-		Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019				
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References					
3.9 EXISTING ROOF TOP WITH UNSAFE PROTECTION FOR MAINTENANCE AND CONSTRUCTION TEAM		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Roof edge protection required during construction of new plant enclosure and installation 2. Existing drainage and access control to be maintained 											
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex			
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood			

Exhibit 13b: Arrangements of proposed safety systems at roof top

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >		INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References			
3.9.1- ROOF TOP PLANTS INSTALLATIONS WITH MANSAFE SYSTEM UNDER CONSTRUCTION	<p>Site Visit 4th March 2019</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mansafe system installed but not being implemented on site now that edge barriers are removed. Handrailed enclosure incomplete. 2. Permit to work system required for roof completion. 3. Harness access system to be available inside plantroom for future access after handover of building. 									
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Constil	App. Insp.	Jay Wood

Exhibit 14a: Visualisation techniques for managing H&S risks

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS																
Project & No:-	Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805	Work Stage :-	4	Revision & Date:	2nd Issue	20 th May 2019													
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References													
1.2 - WINDOWS AND CLEANING	Existing building windows cleaned by long pole be fixed so no opportunity to clean from inside.																				
2.0 CDM ANALYSIS OF PROJECT	KEY TO SYMBOLS					<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Identify Significant Hazards/Risks-only</td> <td>Do this</td> <td>Don't Do This</td> <td>Other Relevant Information</td> </tr> <tr> <td>	TEAM TO ADD SYMBOLS TO DRAWINGS FOR EASE OF CROSS REFERENCING WITH THIS DOCUMENT. ARCHITECTURAL, STRUCTURAL AND M&E CDM REGISTER REQUIRED.														
Identify Significant Hazards/Risks-only	Do this	Don't Do This	Other Relevant Information																		
2.1 PLANNING CONDITIONS	Planning Conditions affecting CDM Issues					TO BE CONFIRMED AFTER APPROVAL															
Team Sign-off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex											
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood											

Exhibit 14b: An excerpt of CDM strategy brief indicating a proposed roof access (See Options Drawings in Exhibit 6)

CDM Strategy Brief - Hazard Identification and Significant Risk Management					ALL SIGNIFICANT RISKS					
Project & No:- Maple Leaf Building, Penn		24805		Work Stage :- 4		Revision & Date: 2nd Issue		20th May2019		
HAZARDS and SIGNIFICANT RISKS	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, , ACTIVITY, LOCATION	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (During early design stages) SFARP	REDUCE or MINIMIZE risks ALARP by :- (During all design stages) Safe systems of work & protection >			INFORMATION To be provided with the design eg Specialist Design & client input	CONTROL METHODS Contractor or Client Manage - ment Systems	ACTIONS & DATES and OTHER SPECIALIST GUIDANCE & COMMENTS Eg. References		
3.6 PROPOSED ROOF ACCESS , PLANTROOM AND PLANT ENCLOSURE	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Existing roof access unacceptable for the increased plant area and roof plant. Pull down ladders in the office space is unacceptable from a tenants viewpoint. Increased open plant enclosure with extended escape distance (upto 60m) acceptable Roof plant enclosure , platform and plant to be lifted onto roof by crane. Size and type of crane to be agreed with curved ramp access constraints. 									
	<p>ROOF PLANT ENCLOSURE PROPOSALS</p> <p>EXISTING DRAW DOWN LADDER ACCESS TO PLANT</p>									
Team Sign -off status	Client	Parker Realty	Architect	Spaysis	Struct. Eng	BM Consult	Services Eng	Solar Eng.	P. Contractor	Limex
Others	PM	Bay Ltd	PD	Spaysis	Landscape		Cost Consultant	PA Consult	App. Insp.	Jay Wood